

Autonomous asteroid imaging, identification, and orbit determination with commercial camera systems

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Abstract

Our research group is actively carrying out feasibility studies on the use of commercial digital cameras for the purpose of autonomous optical navigation of a solar sail-propelled small satellite (SmallSat) to the Martian system. Such miniaturization technologies have already been tested with remarkable success in Low Earth Orbit [1, 2] and even at Mars itself [3]. In the case of our SmallSat, the design of any subsystem is severely constrained, among others, by the overall spacecraft and sail geometries, the space available within the launcher fairing, and the very low thrust derived solely from solar radiation pressure. These strict requirements motivate our search for imaging solutions capable to deliver the greatest accuracy for the smallest mass and volume penalties. As part of this continuing effort, we shall present new data on quantitative comparisons among the calibration frame characteristics of mobile phone cameras and DSLR cameras [4, 5], including our recently acquired Canon 6D Mark II. In particular, we shall discuss the impact of the statistics of such calibrations on star registration, digital asteroid identification [6], and centroid measurement. As part of our plan to test, and later to deploy, a fully self-contained navigation system onboard the vehicle, we shall provide a status report on our transition to a data pipeline and workflow under the Linux operating system. Finally, in order to provide figures of merit for the performance of each imaging subsystem, we shall report on the determination of the orbital elements and corresponding uncertainties of a few test beacon asteroids successfully detected.

1. Introduction

Spacecraft navigation traditionally relies on Earth-based systems such as the Deep Space Network (DSN). However, for missions traveling beyond Earth's immediate environment, these methods face severe latency and dependency issues. Autonomous navigation based on optical methods (OpNav) offers a promising alternative. [1]

This work contributes to the development of a deployable optical navigation tool for a solar sail-propelled SmallSat targeting Mars. After initial validation with images of Comet C/2023 A3, images

contributed by Melisa Gündoğdu, the system transitioned to asteroid (10) Hygiea for demonstrating moving object detection, images contributed by Asst. Prof. Dr. Fabrizio Pinto. We present results from centroid detection, image alignment, blinking sequence analysis, and differential imaging for moving object isolation. The methods and results pave the way for future work on precise orbit determination for both the spacecraft and target objects.

2. Methodology

2.1 Selection of Suitable Locations for Imaging

One of the advantages of living in Izmir, one of the largest cities in Türkiye and located in the Aegean Region, is the abundance of alternative locations for photography, whether along the coastline or in large open areas. Locations have been identified where light pollution — a critical factor in astrophotography — is minimal and where accommodation options are available. The 2023 light pollution map from *Lightpollutionmap.info* was analyzed for this purpose. The shooting locations included Çeşme, Seferihisar, Dikili, and Ozdere. The images selected for further study were taken in Dikili and Ozdere.

Figure 1. Light Pollution Map (<https://www.lightpollutionmap.info/>) and locations where observations were carried out.

2.2 Weather Condition Monitoring and Moon Phase Analysis

For weather monitoring, Türkiye's national meteorology website, the General Directorate of Meteorology, was utilized alongside *Clear Outside* for more detailed analysis. *Clear Outside* provided comprehensive information such as the Moon's phase and rise times, periods of lower cloud coverage, wind data, humidity levels, and optimal time windows for astrophotography. Additionally, multiple sources — including *Space Weather Live*, *kalender-365.de*, *timeanddate*, *phasesmoon*, *fullmoonphase*, *moon.nasa.gov*, and *space.com* — were consulted to obtain accurate information regarding the Moon's condition. While the primary objective was to capture images during the new moon phase, the rise and set

times of the Moon during other phases — excluding the full moon — were also analyzed to optimize observation scheduling. Based on these analyses, shooting dates were determined accordingly.

2.3 Features and Shooting Settings of the Phone and Camera Used for Shooting

2.3.1 Features and Shooting Settings of the Phone

Feature	Huawei P30 Pro
Main Camera	40 MP, f/1.6, 27mm (wide), OIS
Second Camera	8 MP, f/3.4, 125mm (5x optical zoom), OIS
Third Camera	20 MP, f/2.2, 16mm (ultra-wide)
Fourth Camera	TOF 3D depth sensor
Zoom Capability	5x optical zoom, 10x hybrid zoom, 50x digital zoom
Video Resolution	4K UHD 30fps
Front Camera	32 MP, f/2.0
Night Mode	Yes, excellent low-light performance
HDR Support	Yes
Additional Camera Features	Super Spectrum Sensor, RYYB Color Filter
Battery Capacity	4200 mAh
Operating System	Android (EMUI)

Table 1. Camera features of Huawei P30 Pro model phone.

Huawei P30 Pro model phone was used. The captures were performed using the Pro shooting mode and Manual mode of the smartphone. The ISO setting was adjusted to 1600, the Exposure Value Compensation was set to 0, and Auto Focus Continuous (AF-C) along with Auto White Balance (AWB) were selected. For exposure time, the phone's minimum (1/4000 s), optimal (3.2 s) — based on the 500 Rule formula — and maximum (30 s) capabilities were utilized.

2.3.2. Features and Shooting Settings of the Camera

Feature	Description
Sensor	35mm Full Frame CMOS sensor
ISO Range	100–40000 (expandable: 50–102400)
Live View	Live View with 5x and 10x magnification for focusing
RAW Format	Supports RAW shooting
Long Exposure Noise Reduction	Automatic noise reduction after long exposures
GPS Feature	Built-in GPS for location recording
General Settings Recommendation	Manual mode, ISO 1600–3200, wide aperture (f/2.0–f/2.8)

Table 2. Canon EOS 6D Mark II, DSLR model camera features.

A Canon EOS 6D Mark II camera was used for the captures. The lens employed was a 50mm f/1.4.

During the shooting sessions, ISO was set to 3200, the aperture was adjusted to f/2.0, and exposure times of 1/4000 s and 8 s — the latter determined according to the 500 Rule formula — were utilized.

2.4 Types of Frames Used and Observation Setup

2.4.1 Types of Frames Used

Calibration processes were conducted using four different types of frames: light, dark, bias, and flat frames. All frames were taken in RAW and CR2 format.

Light frames are the main images that capture the actual object you are photographing. Dark frames are images taken with the same exposure settings as the light frames, but with the lens cap on, used to capture the camera's thermal noise and hot pixels. Bias frames are very short exposure images (fastest possible shutter speed) taken with the lens cap on, used to measure the camera's readout noise. Flat frames are images taken of a uniformly illuminated surface to correct for dust spots, vignetting, and uneven illumination in the optical system.

For the smartphone captures, 20–30 images were taken for each frame type. During flat frame acquisition, a white T-shirt and a white light source were used, while a black T-shirt and cardboard were employed for dark and bias frames.

For the DSLR captures, approximately 120 images were taken for the light frames and around 40 images for the calibration frames. In flat frame acquisition, a white T-shirt and a white light source were again utilized, whereas the lens cap was used for dark and bias frames.

Optimal exposure times were used for light and dark frames, while the minimum possible exposure time was used for flat and bias frames.

Following the processing of the images captured with the camera in DeepSkyStacker, the desired results could not be obtained. In response, corrective measures were undertaken by initially reducing the number of flat frames, followed by systematic trials with exposure times of 1/2000 s, 1/1000 s, and 1/500 s. The experimental results indicated that, for smartphone-based flat frames, an exposure time of 1/4000 s yielded the optimal outcome, whereas for camera-based flat frames, an exposure time of 1/500 s produced the most satisfactory results.

Figure 2. Setup for flat frames.

Figure 3. Setup for dark and bias frames.

2.4.2 Observation Setup

Figure 4. Observation setup with phone.

Figure 5. Observation setup with camera.

2.5 Post-Processing Applications

To enhance image quality and reduce noise, *DeepSkyStacker* was utilized; *GIMP* was employed for file size reduction and histogram adjustments; *Astrometry.net* was used for the automatic identification of the captured fields and stars; *ASTAP* and *AstroImageJ* was employed to determine the exact sky position (RA and Dec coordinates) of each captured image; *Stellarium* was utilized to realistically visualize the night sky based on date, time, and location, and to enable comparison with the captured images; and *MetaData++* was used to retrieve GPS coordinates, timestamps, and other capture details from the photographs.

2.6 Targeted Objects During Imaging

2.6.1 Photos Taken by Phone

Figure 6. DATE-OBS: 2024-10-28T16:59:57.000, LOCATION: 27.66 (GPS Altitude), 39;7;6.61285400000633 (GPS Latitude), 26;51;21.3079830000059189 (GPS Longitude).

Figure 7. Cropped version of Figure 6.

Figure 8. Astrometry.net result of Figure 7.

Figure 9. Asteroid and comet annotation of Figure 7 on ASTAP.

Figure 10. Star (database) annotation of Figure 7 on ASTAP.

When the same location and time information were entered into Stellarium, it was observed that there were differences of only a few seconds or milliseconds between the RA and Dec values. For instance:

Expected Coordinates of HIP 86511:
 17h 40m 44.05s,
 +4° 9' 10.7'

Measured Coordinates of HIP 86511:
 17h 40m 44.29s,
 +4° 9' 10.7'

2.6.2 Photos Taken by Camera

Figure 11. The monochrome-converted version of the .fits file obtained from Astrometry.net for the light frame captured on 2025-04-20. DATE-OBS: 2025-04-20T22:05.000, LOCATION: 6.8 (GPS Altitude), 38; 2; 58.7159999999858044 (GPS Latitude), 27; 2; 50.2379999999975695 (GPS Longitude).

Figure 12. The monochrome-converted version of the .fits file obtained from Astrometry.net for the light frame captured on 2025-04-21. DATE-OBS: 2025-04-21T20:25.000, LOCATION: 3.3 (GPS Altitude), 38; 2; 59.5139999999955904 (GPS Latitude), 27; 2; 48.75 (GPS Longitude).

Figure 13. The monochrome-converted version of the .fits file generated by Astrometry.net after processing the photographs dated 2025-04-21, with DeepSkyStacker.

Figure 14. First Light Example of 2025-04-21 (to be developed).

2.7 Transition to a Linux-Based Processing Environment

To ensure stability and have an easier usage of open-source technologies, the entire pipeline was switched to Linux (Ubuntu). Installed software included a local Astrometry.net server, NumPy, SciPy, AstroPy, OpenCV libraries, and Source Extractor (SExtractor) along with Python 3.13. This setup met the operational needs for future deep-space missions by allowing fully offline, autonomous processing.

2.8 Initial Work with Comet C/2023 A3

Our first experimental phase involved processing images of Comet C/2023 A3 provided by Melisa Gündoğdu. These images served two key purposes. Validation of the local Astrometry.net server in solving sky fields and generating World Coordinate System (WCS) data, and the testing of Source Extractor configuration for faint object detection in astronomical scenes. Using the local pipeline, we successfully identified background stars, performed centroid measurements, and cross-verified them against the SIMBAD astronomical database.

Figure 15. Processed image of Comet C/2023 A3 annotated with detected stars

2.9 Focus Shift: Asteroid (10) Hygiea

Recognizing the need to demonstrate asteroid detection and motion tracking, the project transitioned to using images of asteroid (10) Hygiea. High-resolution images of asteroid (10) Hygiea were contributed by Asst. Prof. Dr. Fabrizio Pinto. The images captured the asteroid's motion against a static star background, providing an ideal dataset for moving object detection testing.

Figure 16. Initial unprocessed frame showing asteroid (10) Hygiea among background stars.

3. Image Processing and Navigation Algorithm Development

3.1 Local Astrometry.net Network Setup and Usage

In order to handle various fields of view, Astrometry.net was installed locally utilizing index files from the 4100 and 5200 series. The local solve-field function was used to generate WCS (World Coordinate System) headers for every astronomical image.

Because it allowed the navigation process to convert pixel data to celestial coordinates without the need for ground-based support, this was crucial for autonomous deep space operation. The annotation of solved images with known star positions served as a crucial reference for matching, aligning, and verifying placements.

The spacecraft's imaging system can now perform real-time celestial placement without the need for ground involvement thanks to a fully functional offline astrometric calibration process. This is a critical milestone for deep-space autonomy.[11]

```

ayten@ayten-IdeaPad-Gaming-3-15IMH05: ~
Field 1 did not solve (Index Index-4117.fits, field objects 11-20).
no field stars:
star 8; field_xy 764.6,882.7, field_orlg 764.6,882.7
star 10; field_xy 103.3,107.5, field_orlg 103.3,107.5
star 5; field_xy 517.0,830.3, field_orlg 517.0,830.3
log-odds ratio 27.8789 (5.75719e+11), 8 match, 0 conflict, 24 distractors, 28 Index.
RA,Dec = (206.827,2.95104), pixel scale 36.3099 arcsec/pix.
Hit/miss: Hit/miss: -----*(best)-----
Field 1: solved with Index Index-4116.fits.
Field 1 solved: writing to file ./autosave-10bit-mono-detail-1-astroid-annotation-2.solved to indicate t
his.
Field: autosave-10bit-mono-detail-1-astroid-annotation-2.fits
Field center: (RA,Dec) = (206.840814, 2.95623) deg.
Field center: (RA H:M:S, Dec D:M:S) = (17:47:21.795, +02:57:23.879).
Field size: 13.7465 x 10.8251 degrees
Field rotation angle: up is 35.0211 degrees E of N
Field parity: pos
Creating new FITS file "annotated.fits"...
Creating Index object overlay plot...
Creating annotation plot...
Your field contains:
The star 09ph
The star 530ph
The star Cebalrai / cheleb (80ph)
The star 09ph
The star 2ser
The star 860ph
The star 870ph
The star 880ph
The star 780ph
The star 730ph
The star 740ph

```

Figure 17. Schematic of local Astrometry.net solving process.

3.2 Source Extractor Configuration and Object Detection

Source Extractor (SExtractor) was employed to perform robust object detection and photometric analysis within each astronomical image.

After the installation of necessary libraries including, but not limited to FFTW, ATLAS, CLAPACK, the configuration file parameters were optimized to detect stars within an image field. After configuration, each frame was processed to produce an output catalog that consisted of all detected sources, along with measured positions, fluxes, and shape parameters.

The ASSOC feature was used to cross-match detected objects with external catalogs, such as SIMBAD star lists, validating detection accuracy. Object lists from Source Extractor provided a secondary method to confirm the consistency of star positions. [9]

3.3 Centroid Detection of Objects and Neighbor Matching

As we moved on to 10 Hygiena, Python was utilized in order to identify asteroids. Centroids of stars and space objects were identified based on their intensity and threshold. Once centroids were extracted for each frame, a neighbor-based matching algorithm compared detected objects across consecutive frames. By identifying pairs of stars that remained stationary, the pipeline calculated the required image shifts, rotations, and scalings needed to align all frames accurately.

Following alignment, OpenCV was used to generate a "blinking" animation to manually detect the asteroid through its apparent motion relative to stationary background stars — a classical but powerful method in asteroid detection [10].

Figure 18.1: Aligned Frame-1 of sky containing 10 Hygiena

Figure 18.2: Aligned Frame-2 of sky containing 10 Hygiena

Figure 18.3: Aligned Frame-3 of sky containing 10 Hygiena

3.4 Differential Imaging and Isolation of Moving Object

To enhance asteroid visibility, forward and backward difference images were computed. This method successfully highlighted the starting and ending positions of (10) Hygiea across the dataset, isolating the moving target from the star field.

Upon isolation, the asteroid was manually annotated using its pixel coordinates. The final, most visible image frame was uploaded to the local Astrometry.net server and processed through Source Extractor for verification of astrometric accuracy and centroid measurement consistency.

Figure 19.1: Differential image highlighting the start position of the asteroid (backward difference)

Figure 19.2: Differential image highlighting the end position of the asteroid (forward difference)

4. Results and Discussion

The developed pipeline successfully detected asteroid (10) Hygiea, verified its motion against stationary background stars, and accurately localized its centroid. Manual blinking confirmed the object's

displacement across aligned frames, and differential imaging further emphasized its trajectory.

The integration of lightweight, commercial-grade imaging and open-source tools demonstrated a pathway for autonomous deep-space navigation with minimal mass, power, and computational requirements — key factors for solar sail-propelled SmallSat missions.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

This study marks a significant step toward the realization of a fully autonomous optical navigation system suitable for miniaturized spacecraft. Through careful centroid detection, neighbor-based matching, and differential imaging, we demonstrated successful asteroid detection and verification entirely onboard Linux environments using compact imaging systems.

Future work will focus on the precise orbital element calculation of the detected asteroid and, by extension, the spacecraft's position using inverse astrometric methods [7,8]. These results will support final validation steps toward deploying an operational autonomous navigation system for future missions to Mars and beyond.

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7. References

[1] ESA, “Earth through a 2-mm lens,” 08-11-2023, The European Space Agency, https://www.esa.int/ESA_Multimedia/Images/2023/11/Earth_through_a_2-mm_lens, Accessed 25 March 2025.

[2] ArkEdgeSpace, “ArkEdge Space Achieves World-Class Ground Resolution Imaging with ONGLAISAT, a Jointly Developed CubeSat,” 2025-02-7, https://arkedgespace.com/en/news/2025-02-07_onglaisat, Accessed 25 March 2025.

- [3] A. Good, "NASA's First Image of Mars from a CubeSat," JPL, 22 October 2018, <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/nasas-first-image-of-mars-from-a-cubesat/>, Accessed 25 March 2025.
- [4] R. K. Buchheim, *Astronomical Discoveries You Can Make, Too!* (Springer, Cham, Switzerland, 2015).
- [5] M. Zhang, "Precision Multiband Photometry with a DSLR Camera," *Publ. Astron. Soc. Pac.*, 128, 035001 (2016).
- [6] Z. Du et al., "Deep learning-assisted near-Earth asteroid tracking in astronomical images," *Adv. Space Res.*, 73, 5349-5362 (2024).
- [7] A.O. Sivashli et al., "Autonomous Optical and Inertial Navigation of a Solar-sail Propelled CubeSat Class Spacecraft Targeting Mars and its Moons", Zenodo (2023).
- [8] B. Fu, E. Sperber, F. Eke, "Solar sail technology: A state of the art review", *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, 86 (2016).
- [9] E. Bertin, S. Arnouts, "SExtractor: Software for source extraction", *Astronomy and Astrophysics Supplement Series* (1996).
- [10] F. Pinto, "Introduction to asteroid detection, centroid characterization, and orbit determination" (2022).
- [11] D. Lang et al., "Astrometry.net: Blind astrometric calibration of arbitrary astronomical images", *The Astronomical Journal* (2010).